

Association between Job Satisfaction, Motivation and Five Factors of Organizational Citizenship Behavior

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Abstract—The research aims to study the association between job satisfaction, motivation and the five factors of organizational citizenship behavior (i.e. Altruism, Conscientiousness, Sportsmanship, Courtesy and Civic virtue) among Public Sector Employees in Pakistan. In this research Structure Equation Modeling with confirmatory factor analysis was used to test the relationship between two independent and five dependent variables. Data was collected through questionnaire survey from 152 Public Servants Working in Gujrat District-Pakistan in different capacities. Stratified Random Sampling Technique was used to conduct this survey. The results of the study indicate that five factors of OCB have positive significant relation with both motivation and job satisfaction except the relationship of Civic Virtue with Motivation. The research findings implicate that factors other than motivation and job satisfaction may also affect OCB. Likewise, all the five factors of OCB may not be present in all populations. Thus, Managers must concentrate on increasing motivation and job satisfaction to increase OCB. Furthermore, the present research gives a direction to future researchers to use more independent variables (e.g. Culture, leadership, workplace environment, various job attitudes, types of motivation, etc.) on different types of populations with larger sample size in order to find the reasons behind insignificant relationship of civic virtue with Motivation in the research in hand and to generalize the tested model.

Keywords—Five Factors of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Public Sector Employees in Pakistan.

I. INTRODUCTION

ORGANIZATIONAL Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is emerging as a key area of management research in the 21st Century as it is receiving considerable importance in the context of Organizational Behavior (OB). Knowledge of OCB can be very useful not only for individuals, but also for managers and organizations as a whole. It is indeed a challenge for managers to inspire the workers to demonstrate OCB as it is helpful in improving overall job performance and hence organizational performance [1].

Keeping in view the dire importance of OCB in the organizations this research paper investigates the relationship of Job Satisfaction and Motivation with Five most acknowledged Factors of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) stated by [2]-[4] which were originally proposed by [5] i.e. Altruism, Civic Virtue, Conscientiousness, Courtesy and

Sportsmanship. The willingness of employees in performing tasks which are beyond their prescribed Job requirements is called Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Research on OCB started in 1980's when [6], [7] defined OCB as job behavior which is neither compulsory on the part of the individual nor part of the formal reward system of organizations yet it contributes to the overall effectiveness of the organization.

Job satisfaction is considered as an important predictor of OCB [8]. Therefore, we have selected this variable to study its relationship with factors of OCB. It is defined as "an overall measure of the degree to which the employee is satisfied and happy with the job" [9]. As the relationship between job satisfaction and OCB is established in the literature, however, there is a need to study its directional relationship with factors of OCB [10]. It will enable the managers to enhance OCB as well as Job Satisfaction among the employee thus increasing overall organizational performance. On the other hand, employee behaviors are determined by motivational approaches and relationship between employee behaviors and motivation is well documented in literature. However, the extent and type of the relationship between motivation and individual behaviors, i.e. OCB is need to be clearly defined [11]. Motivation is defined as an internal state which increases the desire or pressure to perform [12].

Individuals work motivation can affect job satisfaction which results in determining OCB demonstrated by individuals [13]. Therefore, both motivation and job satisfaction have been selected to check their combined relationship with factors of OCB.

Various researchers (i.e. [3], [14]) have found the relationship between motivation and OCB in different context.

In Pakistan, public sector organizations as a whole have developed and established Human Resources Practices as compared to other industries. So, this is a dynamic research on OCB particularly in the Asian and Pakistani context as only a few researchers have studied the proposed relationships.

Since there is greater variability in workload, job roles, performance appraisal systems, leadership and other human resource practices among different government departments due to a number of factors, therefore, measuring the OCB of the public servants would make this study more diverse and would help in identifying factors as well as parameters which affects OCB. Moreover, to explore that how and to what extent those factors are related to the different segments of OCB.

It is explored that previous studies have measured the relationship of motivation and job satisfaction with only a few

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factors of OCB exclusively in separate studies, but the combined associations of motivation and job satisfaction with five factors of OCB was only studied by [15]. Therefore, this study discussed and answered various research questions/hypotheses for the organizational leaders, especially for the top management of the different government departments in Pakistan and it will also explore new dimensions of research on OCB.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

OCB, a form of extra role behaviors, received considerable importance in the literature almost three decades ago as various researchers, i.e. [16], [5], [6] started exploring different aspects of OCB. OCB is defined by [5] as: "Individual behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organization. By discretionary, we mean that the behavior is not an enforceable requirement of the role or the job description, that is, the clearer specifiable terms of the person's employment contract with the organization; the behavior is rather a matter of personal choice, such that its omission is not generally understood as punishable."

References [4], [17], and [18] along with various other researchers stated the following five factors of OCB i.e. Altruism, Courtesy, Sportsmanship, Civic Virtue and Conscientiousness. These five dimensions reflect the original concept of OCB [5]. Various Researchers [19] used and found support for only three factors of OCB. Likewise, [20] also used the three factors of OCB i.e. Sportsmanship, Conscientiousness, and Altruism. Reference [14] confirmed the two factors of OCB i.e. Altruism and Generalized Compliance in the Korean context. However, in this study we are focusing on the original five dimensional model of [5] to test the relationship of these five factors with Job Satisfaction and Motivation.

The culture of Pakistan and Asia is generally different from the rest of the world, therefore OCB in this area may differ from the rest of the world as OCB vary in geographic context [21] and it is enacted differently in different cultures [22].

According to [23] one of the significant predictors of OCB is Altruism. It is known as helping behavior which means helping less skilled employees on a voluntary basis or assisting overloaded members or colleagues of the organization in completion of their tasks [3], [24]. Another factor of OCB is known as Conscientiousness which means performing ones assigned task extraordinarily thus exceeding expectations, e.g. completing tasks before deadlines by effective time management [18]. It also refers to performing tasks above formal expectations and requirements with punctuality with optimum use of resources [3].

Conscientiousness can be expressed in the form of certain role behaviors, e.g. displaying certain behavior above what is expected, devotion to work and organization, respecting and obeying procedures, rules, regulations even when there is no check and balance and a lot more [25]. Employees who demonstrate conscientiousness behavior are focused to their

jobs and timelier [26]. They are likely to be hardworking, diligent, and good performers. Conscientiousness is an indicator of motivation [27].

Sportsmanship is the discretionary organizational behavior which contributes to organizational effectiveness and it creates a highly positive work climate [28]. It is "accepting less than ideal circumstances" e.g. avoiding small grievances, etc. [3]. It is generally different from other OCB's and employees displaying sportsmanship will avoid actions which may negatively affect the colleagues or organizations. Moreover, employees showing this behavior more frequently bear with the inconveniences and less likely to complain about the little things in the less than ideal circumstances [26]. Sportsmanship is giving more time to organizational endeavors than whining and complaining [29]. It is the tolerance of on the job problems small problems, performing activities which do not involve complaining attitude, and avoid portraying small issues as huge problems [30].

Courtesy may be described as encouraging the professionally discouraged colleagues [3]. It is a behavior in which employees consider their personal actions on other colleagues. They usually take a proactive stance and do not cause sufferings for other employees [26]. Courtesy may be referred to as providing constructive information to other colleagues [29]. Employees are motivated to demonstrate courtesy in order to prevent chaos, conflict and thus problems within the organization [24].

Courtesy may be demonstrated by giving reminders about pending tasks, passing important information that may affect the individuals as well as intimating individuals about expected problems and issues related to them [30].

Civic Virtue is an important form of OCB. It means and includes participation in the political life of the organization, e.g., voluntarily attending meetings and functions which may benefit the organization, reading intra-office mail, discussing work issues on personal time, voting and speaking up, giving recommendation about improvements in organizational procedures and a lot more [3], [5], [24]. Civic virtue is positively related to work performance [31]. It is the behavior exposed by taking part in the organizational activities which are unofficial, not obligatory, mandatory, but are a source of social cohesiveness within the workplace [22].

Job Satisfaction may be termed as sense of Inner fulfillment and joy achieved when performing a job [32]. Whereas an employee going above and beyond the call of duty and doing things which are not part of his formal job role is said to be demonstrating OCB [1]. Therefore, the mutual relationship of both these variables shall be studied in this research.

Job Satisfaction has vital importance in the field of organizational behavior to understand a variety of organizational outcomes and a large number of studies have been conducted on it. OCB is one of the key outcomes of Job Satisfaction [33], [11]. It is the "joyful and positive emotional state of mind as a result of job appraisal or job experience is known as job satisfaction (JS)" [34].

It is evident from the literature that Job Satisfaction can motivate individuals to perform the extra - role behavior [35].

On the other hand a number of studies in the last two decades have reported significant relationship between job satisfaction and OCB e.g. [2], [8], [10], [11], [14], [36]-[38] etc. Furthermore, it is found that one of the five factors of OCB, conscientiousness and job satisfaction had significant relationship [12].

Keeping in view the strong evidence for mutual relationship of job satisfaction and OCB we shall be using Job satisfaction to test its relationship with the five most recognized factors of OCB individually among public servants working in district Gujrat-Pakistan.

Motivation, Job Satisfaction and OCB are interrelated. The word motivation means “

To move” and it is derived from the Latin word “Movere”. Scholars have been studying motivation since 1930. Motivation is the “set of attitudes and values that predisposes a person to act on a specific goal directed manner” [39]. According to [40], [41] the internal process of activating, guiding and maintaining behaviors, especially the goal oriented behaviors is called Motivation.

There is an inborn power in the individuals which directs them to perform specific tasks and attain desired goals. The process which gives a direction to the individuals in attaining their goals is known as motivation. Intrinsic motivation and Extrinsic Motivation are the two types of motivation where the first is based on the inherent need for self-determination as well as competence, etc. but the second type is increased by the workplace environment i.e. Job environment or external rewards [42].

There is a significant positive relationship between Public Service Motivation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior [14]. Reference [11] used five motivational job characteristics, i.e. Job Variety, Identity, Significance, Autonomy and feedback from Job Characteristics Model of [9] to determine the impact of intrinsic Job motivation on OCB. The two theories, i.e. the social exchange theory [43] and the psychological contract theory [44] also underpinned the relationship of motivational job characteristics and OCB.

Since Motivation now a day is a hot topic in organizations and it has become a challenge for managers to keep their employees motivated to work beyond formal job requirements. Therefore, keeping in view the importance of motivation in organizational life and its role in job attitudes it is another factor to check its relationship and impact on five factors of OCB.

III. THEORETICAL MODEL & RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Following conceptual model and directional hypotheses were derived from the extensive literature review for this study:

- H1: Job Satisfaction and Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with each other
- H2a: Job Satisfaction may have a significant positive relationship with Altruism
- H2b: Job Satisfaction may have a significant positive relationship with Conscientiousness

- H2c: Job Satisfaction may have a significant positive relationship with Sportsmanship
- H2d: Job Satisfaction may have a significant positive relationship with Courtesy
- H2e: Job Satisfaction may have a significant positive relationship with Civic Virtue
- H3a: Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with Altruism
- H3b: Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with Conscientiousness
- H3c: Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with Sportsmanship
- H3d: Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with Courtesy
- H3e: Motivation may have a significant positive relationship with Civic Virtue

Fig. 1 Adopted Model [15] (JS=Job Satisfaction, Mot=Motivation, CV=Civic Virtue, Alt=Altruism, SP= Sportsmanship, Cons= Conscientiousness, Court=Courtesy)

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA COLLECTION

It was a cross sectional study in type and quantitative examination in nature. Furthermore, it was an explanatory study to measure and describe the directional relationship between the variables [45]. The public sector employees working in different capacities within District Gujrat were the target population of this study. This included employees working in different positions in different departments, i.e. Health, Education, Finance, and General Administration, etc. From the Job in Public Sector is considered very tough and hectic in the present years, so it generates the importance of motivation and job satisfaction for employee retention, which help the employees to express sportsmanship, courtesy, conscientiousness, altruism and civic virtue thus as a whole showing citizenship behavior. Moreover, there was greater variation in the responses based on different locations, working environment, job descriptions and mental approaches of the employees belonging from different regions, working in a variety of departments. Therefore, original and accurate data with maximum response rate was collected.

In the present study, probability based Stratified Random

Sampling techniques were used [45], [46]. The whole sampling process was divided into two steps. Firstly, the whole population was divided into a number of strata's consisting of Education Sector, Health Sector, General Administration and Finance Sector. Secondly, based on the stratification 160 employees were randomly selected as a sample from all the strata's.

Primary data were collected directly from the respondents through questionnaire/survey method [45]. The questionnaire survey method was adopted because it is the best and most effective source of data collection in business research. The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section consisted of 10 constructs to attain biographic information, whereas the second section consisted of 31 Likert scale questions (5=Strongly Agree..... 1=Strongly Disagree) to measure two independent and five dependent variables through quantitative measures. Whereas, few reverse scoring questions were also being the part of this questionnaire. The values of the Cronbach's alpha (> 0.80) for the individual items of the instrument as well as the overall value of the Cronbach's alpha elaborated the reliability of the questionnaire. Besides that, principle component analysis was applied to check the validity of the data. As the value of the extraction was greater than 0.9 for every item of the instrument where the minimum required value for a sample size 150-300 to run structure equation model can be 0.7 therefore it was considered that the data has stronger validity [47]. And the instrument was useful in the extraction of maximum information from the respondents.

Primary data collected was entered into statistical software, i.e. SPSS and Statistica by giving each answer a numeric code. To test the hypothesis and to find out the relationship of different variables as described in the theoretical framework and hypothesis Frequency Statistics, Descriptive Statistics, inferential statistics i.e. Correlation were applied to test the hypothesis using the given data. The reliability of the data was tested using Cronbach's Alpha values and factor analysis, whereas the validity of the data was tested using Principle Component Analysis (Extraction Method). Furthermore, Structure Equation Modeling Technique, an advanced technique of multivariate data analysis was applied to find out the relationship among the different exogenous and endogenous variables of the model as shown in the theoretical framework and as hypothesized.

V. DATA ANALYSIS RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Demographic Statistics

This part of the data analysis and results describe the demographic statistics of the sample from which data had been collected. Out of 160 sample population 152 respondents returned the completely filled questionnaires on which the data analysis and results were compiled. As the sample had been proportionally allocated among the sampled Strata based on sample size, therefore the demographic statistics showed that the majority of the sample belonged to Education and Health Departments because they had more employees than

other. The majority of the respondents in the current study were male. This huge difference in the gender ratio is because of several socio-cultural reasons, e.g. restrictions on working in public places with the families, etc. The respondents in the current study belonged to different age groups. However, most of the respondents were aged between 21-40 years in this study. According to the qualification almost all the respondents were having a Bachelor's degree at least which is the minimum criteria for induction into public service.

B. Structure Equation Modeling Technique & Interpretations

To test the entire theoretical model with the help of a single statistical technique which considers all possible information we examined our theoretical model using the Structure Equation Modeling Technique (SEM). SEM is a multivariate data analysis technique that includes various techniques most notably factor analysis and multiple regression analysis. We have used SEM in this study because it is used to examine a series of dependence relationships simultaneously. SEM is particularly useful, and important in testing theories which contain multiple dependence relationships. None other technique enables us to test various aspects of a relationship using a single technique. Hence SEM was the most suitable technique to test the proposed theoretical model in this study [47].

C. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The confirmatory factor analysis is used in SEM to test that how well the measured variables represent the construct. It explains whether the used variables can measure the construct or vice versa [47]. The CFA was run using Statistica Version 7.0. All the seven variables (i.e. Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Civic Virtue, Sportsmanship, Altruism, Courtesy and Conscientiousness) were confirmed as factors in the confirmatory factor analysis as the probability values of all the constructs to confirm these factors were less than 0.05. The results support the finding of [15] additionally the only unconfirmed factor Sportsmanship has also been established in this study.

D. Model Estimates and Analysis

After confirmatory factor analysis, SEM model as shown in Fig. 1 (with the confirmed factors) was run to examine the relationships between endogenous and exogenous variables for hypothesis testing.

The model estimates, including Goodness of fit indices and model summary statistics were extracted from Statistica by running the model in the software. The model estimates, explain the fitness of the model as well as the relationship of exogenous and endogenous variables with one another as per the Structure Equation Model hypothesized for the study.

Goodness of fit measure indicated how well the SEM model reproduced the covariance matrix among the indicator variables. The GFI values range between -1 and +1. The greater is the value the greater is the goodness of fit. The values depicted in Table I indicate the goodness of fit of the current SEM model used in this study. Hence the model is fit

for study [47].

TABLE I
 GOODNESS OF FIT INDICES FOR THE MODEL

Joreskog GFI	0.78
Joreskog AGFI	0.73
RMS Standardized Residual	0.085
Steiger-Lind RMSEA	0.075

The structure equation model presented in Fig. 1 was tested using Statistica version 7.0 statistical software. The parameter estimates values and p value statistics were used to find out the relationship of the variables used in this model. As shown in Table II the relationship of the $js \rightarrow mot$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.649) is confirmed which means that job satisfaction had significant positive and direct relationship with motivation. Therefore, on the basis of about stated results, discussion and interpretations we accept H1 for this study. The acceptance of H1 shall be beneficial for future researches on these variables and the administration may focus on one variable, i.e. Job Satisfaction to enhance the other variable i.e. Motivation and vice versa. The results support the findings of [15] as well as of a number of other researchers. Similarly from the values of $js \rightarrow cv$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.571), $js \rightarrow sp$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.012), $js \rightarrow alt$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.231), $js \rightarrow consc$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.305), $js \rightarrow court$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.192) we can inference that Civic Virtue, Sportsmanship, Altruism, Conscientiousness and Courtesy has a significant and positive relationship with Job Satisfaction in this study. Hence we can inference that by increasing job satisfaction the administration can increase OCB. Reference [15] found sportsmanship and civic virtue had an insignificant relationship with job satisfaction, however, in this study relationship of all five factors of OCB has been established with job satisfaction. Hence we can conclude that relationship of the five factors of OCB with Job Satisfaction was confirmed so we can infer that OCB has directional relationship with Job Satisfaction. So, based on the above stated results, discussion and interpretations we accept H2a, H2b, H2c, H2d and H2e for this study. Moreover, on the basis of confirmation of said hypotheses we also infer that as five of the factors of OCB have a significant relationship with Job Satisfaction hence Job Satisfaction has directional relationship with OCB in the current population which may vary in other geographies and organizational contexts due to various reasons. Moreover, Table II shows the model estimates for the relationship of motivation with the factors of OCB and thus with OCB. The model estimate values of $mot \rightarrow cv$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.864), $mot \rightarrow sp$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.014), $mot \rightarrow alt$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.369), $mot \rightarrow consc$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.279), and $mot \rightarrow court$ ($p=0.00$, parameter estimate =0.293) interpret that Sportsmanship, Altruism, Conscientiousness and Courtesy respectively has significant, positive and directional relationship with motivation in this study. However, as the p value of $mot \rightarrow cv$ relationship is not normal, therefore this relationship is insignificant in this study

due to various factors which may be determined in future researches. The significant relationship of motivation with Sportsmanship, Altruism, Conscientiousness and Civic Virtue is a positive outcome of this study and from this we can inference than by increasing the level of motivation we can increase these factors of OCB thus enhancing overall OCB among employees. The results of relationship of motivation with civic virtue, courtesy as well as sportsmanship are contradictory with the findings of [15] whereas findings in relationship of motivation with Altruism and Conscientiousness support the same study. Therefore, we can conclude for the relationship of motivation with five factors of OCB as shown in the below structure equation model that four factors of OCB had statistically significant relationship with motivation, however, one factor in this study is not confirmed in this model due to non-normal p value. Hence, from this we can infer that as four among five determinants of OCB has a significant positive relationship with motivation therefore OCB also has directional relationship with motivation. So, based on the above stated results, discussion and interpretations we reject H3a for this study, however, we accept H3b, H3c, H3d and H3e for this study. Hence, on the basis of confirmation of aforementioned hypotheses we conclude that OCB has significant and directional relationship with motivation as four dimensions of OCB are positively related with motivation.

TABLE II
 HYPOTHESIS TESTING THROUGH SEM MODEL ESTIMATES

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	Remarks
H ₁	(js)→(motive)	0.649	Positive Significant Association therefore H ₁ Accepted
H _{2a}	(js)→(cv)	0.571	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{2a} Accepted
H _{2b}	(js)→(sp)	0.012	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{2b} Accepted
H _{2c}	(js)→(alt)	0.231	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{2c} Accepted
H _{2d}	(js)→(consc)	0.305	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{2d} Accepted
H _{2e}	(js)→(court)	0.192	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{2e} Accepted
H _{3a}	(mot)→(cv)	-0.012	Insignificant Association therefore H _{3a} Rejected
H _{3b}	(mot)→(sp)	0.014	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{3b} Accepted
H _{3c}	(mot)→(alt)	0.369	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{3c} Accepted
H _{3d}	(mot)→(consc)	0.279	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{3d} Accepted
H _{3e}	(mot)→(court)	0.571	Positive Significant Association therefore H _{3e} Accepted

Note: *Significant at $p < 0.05$ levels

E. Conclusion

In vivid conclusion, we can say that job satisfaction positively affects motivation and both motivation and job satisfaction have positive, significant and directional relationship with factors of OCB as conceptualized in the Fig.1 excluding the relationship of motivation with civic virtue for the present study. The results are an addition and significant contribution to the literature on OCB.

VI. LIMITATIONS

The results of the following study may be considered by keeping in view following limitations:

- a. This represents the behaviors of a specific population of a specific region; however, the behaviors of the public servants of different regions and departments may vary from others.
- b. The study considered only few departments. Whereas there are various departments with limited number of offices and employees hence were not present in the selected population, therefore these results may not be generalized to those public servants.
- c. Only Job Satisfaction and Motivations effect has been tested on OCB in this study, whereas there are so many other factors and Job Attitudes which may affect citizenship behaviors of employees.
- d. Respondents' consideration of English as a foreign language could have affected the responses.

VII. PRACTICAL APPLICATION

This research has various practical applications for the management to develop citizenship behaviors in the employees. Following are the few aspects of the implications:

- a. The management can utilize the information and inferences drawn in this study as well as the tested theoretical model to increase citizenship behaviors by increasing level of motivation.
- b. The management can focus on the tested theoretical model to increase the citizenship behaviors among employees by focusing on job satisfaction.
- c. The management can focus on developing the factors of OCB, which are not present in the current population or are weaker and thus may increase the overall OCB among the employees.
- d. By focusing on the OCB the management will be able to enhance job attitudes, i.e. Job Satisfaction, Motivation, Job Commitment, Job Involvement and various other attitudes, i.e. employee retention, loyalty and organizational efficiency can be increased among the employees by focusing on OCB.

VIII. FUTURE RESEARCH PROSPECTS

This research indicates that Motivation and Job Satisfaction can influence organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), but it does not shed light on the mechanisms through which this can be accomplished.

Future research directions may include:

- a. Longitudinal studies to establish a causal relationship between variables.
- b. Since the study was conducted on limited public servants as respondents, other employees working in the organization can also be selected as respondents to test their level of OCB and to check the influence of different variables on factors of OCB.
- c. To enhance the external validity, the future research efforts may obtain a bigger sample size from other organizations and industries as well.
- d. Different other variables, i.e. Job Commitment, Job Involvement, Leadership Styles etc. may be included to check their impact on OCB of employees.
- e. Moreover, the impact of the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation may be individually tested on the OCB and its factors.
- f. To identify the reasons behind insignificant relationship of civic virtue with motivation in the present study.
- g. Further research is needed to authenticate the validity and reliability of the tools outside Pakistan and to assist making a generalization that Motivation and Job Satisfaction positively affect Organizational Citizenship Behaviors of the employees working in different workplaces.

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